

VIOLENCE AGAINST WOMEN, ITS TYPES AND CONSEQUENCES

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Abstract: The article notes that it is very sad to see when there are some cases of violence which is done by some husbands against women who are bring up their children - flowers and basil of Paradise. There are more and more cases on TV and news from Internet that provoke hatred and protests among people because of mentioned news. This news is just some of reality we've heard about only. How many women are under such kind of pressure to protect their families, those women try to avoid making their children half-orphans. Our national and religious traditions, teach women to respect men from their childhood. But what nation or religion allows a man to force his wife to do such disgusting things? Such kind of acts, first of all, don't acceptable either humanity or morality. Issues such as whether it is supported are covered in the scientific article on the basis of clear arguments.

Keywords: Islam, gender equality, violence, discrimination, upbringing, women's rights, freedom, religiosity.

Of course, in family relationships may happen sometimes misunderstandings and frustrations. Of course, this is usually temporary situation, in case of misunderstandings couples should be forgivable for each other and not to use harmful words, important not to lose respectful relationship for each other. Taking into account such situations, in Quran we can find in ayat 19 of Nisah surah this: "Live with rhem in peace. Even if you dislike them (be patient and live peaceful). After all, Allah may have made many good things in those you see as bad" (The Holy Quran 1992, 70).

It is very sad to see when there are some cases of violence which is done by some husbands against women who are bring up their children - flowers and basil of Paradise. There are more and more cases on TV and news from Internet that provoke hatred and protests among people because of mentioned news. This news is just some of reality we've heard about only. How many women are under such kind of pressure to protect their families, those women try to avoid making their children half-orphans. Our national and religious traditions, teach women to respect men from their childhood. But what nation or religion allows a man to force his wife to do such disgusting things? Such kind of acts, first of all,

don't acceptable either humanity or morality. According to truth hadiths, narrated by Abdullah ibn Zam'a: "Rasulullah sollallahu alayhi wasallam: "He asked, even of you have beaten your wife like a slave" (Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq 2018, 242). It means the importance of women dignity in Islam.

"Discrimination" is exclusion and restriction of person on the basis of its race, sex, language, religion or other grounds, as result; it is violation of human rights. If there is unequal treatment in the presence of equal condition known as discrimination. According to the European Court of Justice, discrimination is the treatment to a person with different way in the same situation in a group of persons. However, being treated differently should not always be accepted as discrimination. If there is no legitimate purpose to justify different treatment, or if the application of different treatment is not in accordance with objective or reasonable purpose, so, it could be discrimination.

Violence is the act, which is prohibited by law and it is directed to harm of person morality, mentality, or physically. The forms of violence are different, so the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan of September 2, 2019 "On Protection of Women from Oppression and Violence" defines violences into four types. They are:

1. Physical violence;
2. Psychological violence;
3. Sexual violence;
4. Economic violence. ("Family" Research Center 2020, 9).

All of these types of violence unfortunately occur in some families. Present day, one of three women worldwide is a victim of physical or sexual violence. 71 percent of victims of human trafficking are women. One of the leading causes of death and disability among reproductive age women are the use of violence acts against them.

Every year, there is a worldwide campaign which includes itself 16 days kown as "Days against Women Violence". This compaign links symbolically 2 major days itself – the beginning of compaign on November, 25 "International Women's Day" and the end December 10 "International Human Rights Day". Such kind of compaign has been successfully organized in Uzbekistan since 2011 under the motto "From peace of home towards the peace of world". On November 26, 2020, in Uzbekistan organized opening ceremony compaign devoted to Against Women Violence, the main topic of this ceremony was: "Taken measures to mitigate COVID-19 impact in pandemic period, its consequences, lessons and further plans".

It is known that from January 4, 2020, by government of Uzbekistan was introduced a protection order for women who are victims of oppression and violence. According to the Ministry of Neighborhood and Family Support, 3,592 women have been issued with protection orders in 7 months. According to the ministry, the number of issued protection orders is higher in Tashkent region, Tashkent city and Bukhara than other regions of the republic. According to information in April 20 of 2020, 14 women and their children placed in rehabilitation and adaptation centers in Andijan, Bukhara, Jizzakh, Samarkand and Surkhandarya regions, because of violence. Now, they are being provided with the necessary legal, psychological and medical assistance. These statistics cannot be free from the temptation of devil until man cannot learn how to work on himself and control his anger. Such kind of acts makes anyone in shame reputation in society. After all, to be happy and to live in a prosperous life is in our hands and depend on us.

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